

PLASTICITY AND INTERNAL STRESS ANALYSIS FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL
METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES DURING DEFORMATION PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

An analysis is conducted for investigating the internal stresses in a unidirectional short fiber-reinforced metal matrix composite (MMC) undergoing large plastic deformation. The approach combined the micromechanics analysis with the macroscopic plasticity model. The micromechanics analysis is based on the Eshelby's inclusion method incorporated with the mean field theory. Proportional loading in the directions of principal anisotropy axes is examined. The general effects of fiber's aspect ratio on the deformation and internal stresses are studied. Based on the same framework, a general yield function is established for describing the macroscopic anisotropic plastic deformation of MMCs. The evolution of the yield surface is also examined.

KEYWORDS: MMC; plasticity, micromechanics; anisotropy; multiaxial loading.

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to improve the mechanical properties of materials, various methods for incorporating the reinforcements into monolithic materials have been developed over the last few years. Among these methods, powder metallurgy, diffusion bonding, and liquid infiltration/pressure casting have received particular attention as the primary processes which manufacture raw metal matrix composites (MMCs) with little or no shape [1-4]. On the other hand, it has been of great interest to make raw MMCs into useful shapes by conventional metalworking practices like forging, rolling, extrusion, and drawing, etc. [3, 5-9]. These processes also tend to improve the microstructure of the matrix material, just like that occurs for the usual metals. Each of these processing methods however gives rise different problems. One of them is the fiber degradation by breakage which occurs almost in every step in fabricating MMCs by rolling [5-8], hot pressing [1], and extrusion [9,10]. For whisker- or short fiber-reinforced MMCs, it has been well received that a sufficient aspect ratio along with adequate bonding and preferential alignment are all vital for reinforcements to be effective. Further, the newly generated fiber's ends by fracture usually possess very weak bonding to the matrix metal, giving rise to voids when subjected to loading. It is anticipated that the ductility will therefore be greatly reduced because of

the severe stress concentrations and the void nucleation originated from the fiber's sharp, closely placed broken ends [11].

Since the fiber breakage imperils the performance of MMCs to a great extent, it became one of the major problems to be overcome not only among the primary manufacturing processes, but also in the secondary forming and shaping operations. The interactions between the matrix metal and the reinforcements in these processes can be categorized into two general types. The first one is represented by a mixture of the matrix powder and the reinforcing whisker/particulate, as typified by hot pressing; the external force is transmitted to the reinforcement through the matrix powder [12]. In the second type of system, the whiskers are embedded in the fully dense metal matrix. Depending on the loading pattern and the fibers' microstructure, fibers can fail in several different mechanisms. Zweben [13] identified three modes of tensile failure: the weakest link, the fiber break propagation, and the cumulative weakening. Some of the efforts in understanding these phenomena are represented by [13-16]. As pointed out by Nairn [16] the major problem is the lacking of a good connection between the macroscopic analysis and the microstructure. Even the approach developed by Nairn [16] is restricted to the usage of a relatively simplified analysis.

This study is aiming at investigating the possibility of fiber fracture in tensile mode by developing a model capable of predicting the fiber stress as the matrix material is undergoing relatively large plastic deformation. The Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method incorporated with the mean field theory [17-22] will be used in this study. In the following, the formulation based on the generalized Eshelby inclusion method is introduced very briefly. The anisotropy of matrix plastic flow induced by fibers is determined by minimizing the composite potential energy. A generalized yield function is proposed, whose parameters are to be determined by using the calculated results from Eshelby inclusion method. Some calculated results regarding the composite deformation and the internal stresses are reported and discussed in a following section, in which the SiC/2014 Al composite system is used as an example.

2 MICROMECHANICS

2.1 Generalized Eshelby Inclusion Method The coordinate system used in this study is depicted in Figure 1. There are two sets of coordinate system: the deformation coordinate system Γ is used with its axes in the direction of major external forces; the inclusion coordinate system Γ' is attached to the inclusion which can make any angle to the deformation coordinate. Particularly, the longest axis of the fiber is always pointed in the 3-axis in the inclusion coordinate system Γ' . We define the orientation angle ϕ_i as the angle made between axes i ($i = 1$ to 3) of Γ and Γ' . During a general deformation the inclusion may rotate with respect to the deformation coordinate. However, this study assumes that the inclusion does not rotate, neither the applied stress changes its direction in the course of deformation.

The generalized Eshelby equivalent inclusion method actually involves three main parts which reflect the evolution of the method to the current form; namely, (I) the Eshelby inclusion theory [17] for single inclusion embedded in an infinite elastically homogeneous body; (II) the elastically inhomogeneous inclusion/matrix system [18,19]; and (III) the mean field theory which takes account of the interactions between inclusions [20-22]. We summarize in the following the generalized Eshelby theory combined with the mean field field.

According to the theory the influences of neighboring inclusions are represented by the so-called mean

stresses denoted by $\langle \sigma \rangle_M$ and $\langle \sigma \rangle_I$ for the matrix and the inclusion, respectively. When there exists an external stress, σ^A , the average stresses in the matrix and the inclusions are

$$\hat{\sigma}_M = \sigma^A + \langle \sigma \rangle_M, \quad \hat{\sigma}_I = \sigma^A + \langle \sigma \rangle_I. \quad (1)$$

The average stress is the volume average of total stress over each phase. This is the stress one might be able to measure. Let ϵ^c be the constrained strain, ϵ^{T^*} and ϵ^T be the transformation strains in the inhomogeneous composite and the equivalent homogeneous system, respectively. The constrained strain ϵ^c is related to the transformation strain ϵ^T by $\epsilon^c = S\epsilon^T$ where S is the fourth-order Eshelby tensor which depends only on the inclusion geometry and the Poisson's ratio of the material [18]. (The S_{1111} of Table 1 in [18] should read $Q\pi + R\Gamma_a + \frac{3}{4}T$). The net strain in the inclusion is $\epsilon^c + \epsilon^A + \langle \epsilon \rangle_M - \epsilon^{T^*}$ for the inhomogeneous composite and $\epsilon^c + \epsilon^A + \langle \epsilon \rangle_M - \epsilon^T$ for the equivalent homogeneous system [20]. Hence the average inclusion stress can be written in the following two ways [20]:

$$\hat{\sigma}_I = C^I(\epsilon^c + \epsilon^A + \langle \epsilon \rangle_M - \epsilon^{T^*}) : \text{Inhomogeneous composite} \quad (2a)$$

$$= C^M(\epsilon^c + \epsilon^A + \langle \epsilon \rangle_M - \epsilon^T) : \text{Equivalent homogeneous composite} \quad (2b)$$

where C^M and C^I are the fourth-order tensors of elastic compliance of matrix and inclusion, respectively. In fact, the transformation strain ϵ^T can be solved from the following equation, providing σ^A and ϵ^{T^*} are given:

$$\epsilon_{mn}^T \left((1-f)C_{ijkl}^M(S_{klmn} - \delta_{km}\delta_{ln}) - C_{ijkl}^I((1-f)S_{klmn} + f\delta_{km}\delta_{ln}) \right) = (C_{ijkl}^I - C_{ijkl}^M)\epsilon_{kl}^A - C_{ijkl}^I\epsilon_{kl}^{T^*} \quad (3)$$

where δ is the Kronecker delta function and f is the volume fraction of inclusion. After ϵ^T is determined the average stress in matrix and fiber are obtained accordingly [23].

For composites loaded at an angle with respect to the fiber direction, the above formulation is still valid simply by transforming the Eshelby tensor S from the inclusion coordinate system (Γ) to the deformation coordinate system (Γ) [23].

2.2 Plastic Deformation The matrix of polycrystalline is assumed to take a multislip pattern during plastic deformation. The plastic flow in the matrix can be represented by a uniform stress-free plastic strain ϵ^P . The stress field generated by the misfit is therefore identical to that of a matrix containing inclusions strained by $-\epsilon^P$ in a stress free manner [20], i.e., $\epsilon^{T^*} = -\epsilon^P$. The transformation strain ϵ^T can be solved from equation (3) and used to determine the total macroscopic composite strain ϵ^{Comp} :

$$\epsilon^{Comp} = \epsilon^A + \epsilon^P + f\epsilon^T. \quad (4)$$

In actual analysis the plastic strain ϵ^P is not known *a priori*, instead, it is determined according to the stress state in the composite. In this regard, the matrix metal is assumed to obey the von Mises yield criterion: $\hat{\sigma}_M^{eff} = Y$, where Y is the *in situ*, or the constrained, flow stress of matrix. The constrained flow stress is different from the flow stress of the unconstrained matrix material. Experimental and theoretical study strongly suggested that the constrained flow stress contains a "shorting term" and another term controlled by the matrix microstructure [20,21]. The intent to predict the constrained flow stress has not been very successful yet [20,21]. In this study, we use the parabolic Ludwik-Hollomon relation [24].

As a preliminary study, this investigation will consider only a small number of special deformation pattern in which the direct plastic strain in matrix appears only in the direction of axes 1, 2, and 3 of the deformation coordinate system Γ (Figure 1); no shear strain is considered. Accordingly, the plastic strain can be represented by

$$\varepsilon^P = \varepsilon^P \begin{pmatrix} -\alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -(1-\alpha) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where α is a scalar whose value might change during deformation. Actually α represents the plastic anisotropy of matrix flow which experiences the constraint imposed by the fibers. We observed that for a predetermined α the corresponding ε^P can be calculated for a given applied stress easily by solving the yield criterion. Therefore, an initial guess of α is used for calculating the value of ε^P . After ε^P is calculated, the correct value of α is determined by minimizing the composite potential energy which is given by [20]

$$PE = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^A \varepsilon^A - \frac{1}{2} f(\sigma^A + \langle \sigma \rangle) \varepsilon^{T*} \quad (6)$$

When α is updated, the ε^P is recalculated accordingly; an iteration procedure is used to determine ε^P and α .

3. ANISOTROPIC PLASTICITY THEORY

As far as the macroscopic plastic deformation is concerned, it is needed to establish a proper yield function that adequately describes the onset of yielding. Besides, an appropriate flow rule and strain hardening rule have to be furnished to describe the evolution of the yield surface. In this section, we elaborate in finding a proper formulation along this line. Because the composite anisotropy is mostly determined by the fiber orientation, the inclusion coordinate system Γ is used in this section.

One of the widely used yield functions for anisotropic materials is Hill's orthotropic yield function [25] which implies incompressibility of plastic deformation. This assumption is valid for most metals, however, we have not proved this for MMCs yet. According to the calculations reported in [23] the volumetric plastic strain is not negligible. Therefore, the Hill's yield function is not totally valid in this regard. Recently, Sun and his colleague [26-28] employed an orthotropic elastic-plastic formulation to characterize the nonlinear behavior of a unidirectional composite. We adopt the idea from [26] but with less restriction for the MMCs. In the following, the composite is treated as a homogeneous material whose properties show directionality. The scale of constituent phases is assumed to be at least one order less than that for measuring the stress and strain in the sense of continuum mechanics. Consequently, there is no distinguish between the fibers and the matrix metal.

A general quadratic yield function for the fiber composite is given by [26] which involves 9 coefficients to describe the state of anisotropy. Just like we did before for the analysis by Eshelby inclusion method, plane isotropy is assumed for both elastic and plastic deformation in the plane perpendicular to the fiber direction (i.e., the plane consists of axes 1 and 2 in inclusion coordinate system Γ). Because of the plane isotropy the yield function should maintain its form if the coordinate system is rotated along the 3-axis ($\phi_3 = 0$, $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi$).

By some manipulation, the general yield function as given by [26] is reduced to

$$2f(\sigma_{ij}) = a_{11}^2 \sigma_{11}^2 + a_{11}^2 \sigma_{22}^2 + a_{33}^2 \sigma_{33}^2 + 2a_{12} \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} + 2a_{13} \sigma_{11} \sigma_{33} +$$

$$2a_{13}\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33} + 2a_4\sigma_{23}^2 + 2a_4\sigma_{31}^2 + 2(a_{11} - a_{12})\sigma_{12}^2 = k. \quad (7)$$

We now focus our attention on a group of deformation which is general enough to include the proportional loading with the applied stress being represented by (in deformation coordinate system, Γ)

$$\sigma^A = \sigma_{33}^A \begin{pmatrix} \xi & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \eta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where ξ and η are specified constants. Specifically, the shear strains ϵ_{13} and ϵ_{23} are assumed zero, as represented roughly by the rolling operation with fibers perpendicular to the rolling direction. Therefore the terms involving a_4 in equation (7) are dropped out.

Let's introduce the following strain ratios:

$$\alpha'_1 = \frac{a_{13}}{a_{33}} = \left(\frac{d\epsilon_{11}^P}{d\epsilon_{33}^P} \right)_L, \quad \alpha'_2 = \frac{a_{12}}{a_{11}} = \left(\frac{d\epsilon_{11}^P}{d\epsilon_{22}^P} \right)_T, \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha'_3 = \frac{a_{13}}{a_{11}} = \left(\frac{d\epsilon_{33}^P}{d\epsilon_{22}^P} \right)_T. \quad (9)$$

where the subscript L stands for the longitudinal loading ($\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{22} = 0$) and T for the transverse loading without lateral loading ($\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{33} = 0$). The yield function can be written as

$$2f(\sigma_{ij}) = \alpha_1\sigma_{11}^2 + \alpha_1\sigma_{22}^2 + \alpha_3\sigma_{33}^2 + 2\alpha_2\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 2\alpha_3\sigma_{11}\sigma_{33} + 2\alpha_3\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33} + 2(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)\sigma_{12}^2 = k. \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha_1 = \alpha'_1/\alpha'_3$, $\alpha_2 = \alpha'_2\alpha_1$, and $\alpha_3 = \alpha'_1$. By assuming that the associated flow rule is valid and after some manipulation, one can write the incremental plastic strains as

$$\begin{pmatrix} d\epsilon_{11}^P \\ d\epsilon_{22}^P \\ d\epsilon_{33}^P \\ d\gamma_{12}^P \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \alpha_2 & \alpha_3 & 0 \\ \alpha_2 & \alpha_1 & \alpha_3 & 0 \\ \alpha_3 & \alpha_3 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 - \alpha_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix} d\lambda \quad (11)$$

where $d\lambda$ is the non-negative proportionality and $\gamma_{12} = 2\epsilon_{12}$ is the engineering shear strain.

Similar to the plasticity formulation for isotropic materials, it is desirable to develop an effective measure of stress and plastic strain for anisotropic materials. Let the effective stress be defined by

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sqrt{2f}. \quad (12)$$

Using the concept of plastic work, we obtain the effective incremental plastic strain as

$$d\bar{\epsilon}^P = (\alpha_1 A_1^2 + \alpha_1 A_2^2 + A_3^2 + 2\alpha_2 A_1 A_2 + 2\alpha_3 A_1 A_3 + 2\alpha_3 A_2 A_3 + \frac{2(\gamma_{12}^P)^2}{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2})^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

where A_i ($i = 1$ to 3) are given by

$$A_1 = \frac{(\alpha_1 - \alpha_3^2)d\epsilon_{11}^P + (\alpha_3^2 - \alpha_2)d\epsilon_{22}^P + \alpha_3(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)d\epsilon_{33}^P}{(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 2\alpha_3^2)}$$

$$A_2 = \frac{(\alpha_3^2 - \alpha_2)d\epsilon_{11}^P + (\alpha_1 - \alpha_3^2)d\epsilon_{22}^P + \alpha_3(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)d\epsilon_{33}^P}{(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 2\alpha_3^2)}$$

$$A_3 = \frac{-\alpha_3d\epsilon_{11}^P - \alpha_3d\epsilon_{22}^P + (\alpha_1^2 - \alpha_2^2)d\epsilon_{22}^P}{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 2\alpha_3^2)}$$

There are two important issues remained. First, the presentation of effective stress and effective plastic strain has not been validated yet. That is, whether or not the functional form $\bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma}(\bar{\epsilon}^P)$ hold for a general deformation. Second, the parameters α_1 , α_2 , and α_3 have yet been determined. This is to be discussed in the following section.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formulation outlined in the preceding section has been applied to SiC/2014 Al composites. In this study, the deformation due to differential thermal expansion between fibers and matrix will not be considered. The mechanical properties of the 2014 aluminum and whisker SiC were adopted from [20] and [29], they are shown as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E^M &= 73 \text{ GPa}, & \nu^M &= 0.32, & Y_0 &= 400 \text{ MPa}, \\ E^f &= 430 \text{ GPa}, & \nu^f &= 0.17, & & \end{aligned}$$

where E and ν are the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio, respectively, and Y_0 is the initial yield stress of the aluminum matrix.

4.1 Longitudinal Loading

In the following, we mainly focus on the effects of fiber's aspect ratio; several other parameters are studied and reported elsewhere [23]. For the cases with applied stress in the reinforcing direction, i.e., $\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{22} = 0$ ($\xi = \eta = 0$), both the stress and the strain fields are axisymmetric with respect to the 3-axis. We refer this type of loading as the longitudinal loading in this paper. The plastic strain is given by equation (5) with α taking the obvious value of 0.5. Figure 2 gives the curve of applied stress σ_{33}^A versus overall composite strain, $\epsilon_{33}^{\text{Comp}}$ (equation (4)). If the uniaxial yield stress of the composite is defined as the stress which makes the matrix start yielding, the composite yield stress is much higher than the matrix yield stress according to Figure 2. For example, for the composite of fiber content 20% and aspect ratio 10, the axial initial yield stress of the composite is raised to 712 MPa from 400 MPa of the matrix metal. According to the same figure, a linear hardening is observed in the region after initial yielding, which is a certain result of the

Eshelby's inclusion method [20].

The effects of fiber content and aspect ratio on the overall plastic behavior of a composite loaded in the reinforcing direction are also evident in Figure 2. Qualitatively, higher aspect ratio and higher fiber content both tend to raise the composite initial yield stress, $\sigma_{33}^A / d \epsilon_{33}^{Comp}$, as well as the strain hardening rate, $\kappa = d \sigma_{33}^A / d \epsilon_{33}^{Comp}$. More quantitative information is given in Figure 3 in which the initial yield stress as well as the strain hardening rate increase at a much higher rate at small aspect ratios than that at large aspect ratios.

Figure 4 gives the fiber stress $(\sigma_{33}^f)_0$ and the increase rate $\kappa^f = \Delta \sigma_{33}^f / \Delta \epsilon_{33}^{Comp}$ as a function of the aspect ratio.

Very pronounced effect of the aspect ratio on the fiber stress has been observed. Nonetheless, the effects of aspect ratio become saturated as the aspect ratio is larger than about 10.

4.2 Transverse Loading

In the following, the deformation of composites under compressive transverse loading is to be examined. In this situation the inclusion coordinate system Γ' rotates with respect to the deformation coordinate system Γ by 90° such that $\phi_1 = 0, \phi_2 = \phi_3 = 90^\circ$. In the deformation coordinate system Γ , the applied stress is considered to take the form of equation (8) with $\xi = 0$. That is, the stress σ_{33}^A is applied transversely while $\sigma_{22}^A = \eta \sigma_{33}^A$ applied in the fiber direction. σ_{22}^A is referred as the lateral loading in this paper. For this type of loading with nonzero force perpendicular to the reinforcement, the plastic strain is given by equation (5) with two unknowns, ϵ^P and α which are determined by the procedure outlined in the previous section.

Since the compressive loading is the main theme for the moment, the convention of metal forming is adopted here; i.e., a compressive stress or strain are regarded as positive. However, the fiber stress still maintains its original sign, i.e., positive fiber stress means tensile.

We first consider the case when there is no lateral loading ($\eta = 0$). The overall stress-strain relationship is shown in Figure 5 for a range of fiber's aspect ratio. Generally, the composite uniaxial flow stress in the

Figure 1. Coordinate system used in the analysis. Γ : Deformation coordinate system, Γ' : Inclusion coordinate system.

Figure 2. The overall stress-strain curve of the composite loaded in the fiber direction.

Figure 3. Composite initial yield stress γ_{O}^{Comp} and the strain hardening rate κ as a function of the aspect ratio, $f = 0.2$.

Figure 4. Fiber stress at matrix initial yielding, σ_{O}^f , and its increase rate, κ^f , as a function of the aspect ratio, $f = 0.2$.

transverse direction is much lower than that in the longitudinal direction (see Figure 2). Also, very little difference on the flow stress has been observed between the MMCs containing fibers of different aspect ratio. This is a strong contrast to that of the longitudinal loading as represented by Figure 2. The fiber stress in transverse loading is due to the triaxial stress state of the matrix in contrast to the direct load sharing associated with the longitudinal loading. As a result, the axial fiber stress is greatly reduced during transverse loading to favor retaining the fibers without fracture. It is also found that the fiber stress corresponding to the cases in Figure 5 only experience small increase when the aspect ratio changes from 2.5 to 20 [23]. In other words, fibers with larger aspect ratio do not suffer too much higher tensile stress than the shorter fibers do. Hence, we may conclude that for composites undergoing transverse deformation without lateral loading the aspect ratio possesses limited effects on both the composite overall stress-strain relation and the fiber axial stress.

It is always a good practice to explore the possibility of reducing the level of fiber stress/strain. One reason is that larger difference between the fiber strain and the matrix strain could imply larger shear strain along the interface, which promotes interfacial failure. Since the axial stress in the fiber is tensile during a compressive transverse loading, it is natural to impose a compressive force in the fiber direction to bring down the tensile fiber stress. When a lateral loading is applied ($\eta > 0$), the curves of the fiber stress is shown in Figure 6 for a range of η . It is shown that although the lateral loading only results in marginally higher applied stress to reach a given composite strain [23], the fiber stress does experience drastic changes. The fiber stress decreases at a rate almost proportional to the value of η , it even becomes compressive at a η larger than 0.4. Consequently, a proper lateral loading can be used to control the axial fiber stress during transverse deformation.

Along this line, it is interesting to find out how to realize the loading condition which ensures an η of about 0.4. We are particularly interested in the plane-strain deformation which is easy to be furnished. To this end, the values of η which lead to zero composite strain in the fiber direction, ε_{22}^{Comp} , are calculated (by second-order interpolation) for composites of different composition. It is found that the value of η which leads to plane-strain deformation is only slightly higher than 0.4 and increases mildly with applied stress σ_{33}^A [23]. That is, during the plane-strain deformation, the side pressing pressure ranges slightly higher than 40% of the major pressing pressure which is perpendicular to the fibers, and the percentage keeps rising with higher major

pressing pressure. It is shown that the value of η decreases with composite's degree of anisotropy. Theoretically, $\eta = 0.5$ for isotropic material undergoing plastic deformation. According to Figure 6, the axial fiber stress tends to become compressive for $\eta \geq 0.4$; hence, the fiber stress would be compressive if a plane strain deformation is strictly maintained. One might conclude that a plane-strain deformation is probably a better deformation pattern to prevent fibers from fracturing. This explains why the fibers' aspect can be best retained during a rolling operation in which the fibers are perpendicular to the rolling direction and are parallel to the roller axes [5-8].

4.3 Macroscopic Plasticity Theory We now discuss the remaining issues as mentioned in a previous section regarding the general yield function of equation (10). Although the parameters α_1 , α_2 and α_3 can be determined experimentally, we choose to establish the model on the framework of the generalized Eshelby inclusion method. In the following, a composite containing fibers of aspect ratio $a = 10$ and content 20% is used mainly as a representative, composites of other composition are studied and reported elsewhere.

The ratios of plastic strain increments as defined by equation (9) are calculated for the composite with $a = 10$ and $f = 0.2$. These ratios maintain unchanged except at small strains [23]. As we mentioned earlier, the strain ratios α'_1 and α'_3 have to be determined at the same measure of plastic deformation in calculating the parameters α_1 . For instance, the plastic work can be a valid measure (although the hypothesis regarding the functional relations among effective stress, effective plastic strain, and plastic work remains to be demonstrated). Fortunately, we found that the strain ratio α'_1 is virtually unchanged for this particular composite in the considered range of strain; the parameters α_1 , α_2 and α_3 are readily determined, as shown in Figure 7. The values of α_1 and α_2 change rapidly with the effective plastic strain while α_3 basically remains unchanged.

Once the parameters α_1 , α_2 , and α_3 are determined for a specific composite the curve of effective stress versus effective plastic strain can be determined for any specified loading to test the hypothesis of plastic function. In this respect, the curve corresponding to the previously discussed transverse and longitudinal loading are determined and shown in Figure 8. Evidently, the effective stress-strain curves for both loading condition collapse into one very well, indicating that the same functional form is kept for loading in each anisotropy axis.

Figure 5. The overall stress-strain curve of the composite for a range of aspect ratio during transverse loading, $f = 0.2$.

Figure 6. The effects of lateral loading on the fiber stress for composite under transverse loading, $a = 10$, $f = 0.2$.

Figure 7. The change of anisotropy parameters, α_1 , α_2 and α_3 , of the proposed yield function.

Figure 8. Curves of effective stress-effective plastic strain for longitudinal loading and transverse loading.

We now examine the proposed yield function in equation (10) as applied to two representative types of deformation, namely, the plane stress and plane strain deformation. In addition, we wish to examine more carefully the applicability of Hill's anisotropy yield function [25]. For plane stress deformation with $\sigma_{33} = 0$, the yield function represented by equation (10) can be simplified as

$$\sigma^2 = \alpha_1^2 \sigma_{11}^2 + \alpha_1^2 \sigma_{22}^2 + 2\alpha_2 \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} + 2(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \sigma_{12}^2 \quad (14)$$

The yield surface on the plane of principal stress is shown in Figure 9 for two levels of ϵ^P . Significant difference from the behavior of isotropic materials is observed. The anisotropy effect becomes more pronounced at larger effective plastic strain. The corresponding expression based on Hill's anisotropy yield function can be derived as

$$\frac{2}{\sigma_{11}^2 + \sigma_{22}^2} - \left(2 - \frac{X^2}{Z^2}\right) \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} = X^2 \quad (15)$$

where X and Z are the flow stress in the principal directions 1 and 3, respectively. The values of X and Z are readily available from our previous calculations based on Eshelby method. The yield surface represented by equation (15) is shown in Figure 9. The difference between equations (14) and (15) is already very obvious at a very low level of effective plastic strain (0.779 %), we expect the difference to become bigger as deformation proceeds.

For plane strain deformation, the plastic strain in the fiber direction is zero. By using the flow rule and having the plastic strain in the direction of 3-axis to be zero, we obtain the yield function as

$$\sigma^2 = (\alpha_1 - \alpha_3^2) (\sigma_{11}^2 + \sigma_{22}^2) + 2(\alpha_2 - \alpha_3^2) \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} + 2(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2) \sigma_{12}^2 \quad (16)$$

The yield surface is plotted as almost straight lines on the plane of principal stress in Figure 9. Although it is not shown in this figure, equation (16) clearly indicates that the yield surface is actually an ellipse. At $\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{22}$, equation (16) is reduced to $\sigma^2 = 2(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 2\alpha_3^2) \sigma_{11}^2$. The coefficient of σ_{11}^2 is therefore very small in this expression such that σ_{11} tends to become very large for a specified σ ; the length of the major axis is much

larger than the minor axis. On the other hand, the corresponding expression for Hill's function is

$$C(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + 4C\sigma_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (17)$$

where $C = \frac{1}{\lambda^2} - \frac{1}{4\lambda^2}$. Equation (17) is really a straight line on the plane of principal stress. It is observed that the difference between (51) and (52) is small as long as the two principal stresses σ_{11} and σ_{22} are not too close.

A last remark is on the relation between a global deformation/stress analysis and the internal stress/strain at the level of constituent phases. As we have seen before, the generalized Eshelby method and all other micromechanics models cannot reflect the effects of global constraint directly. To the best, these models can only convey the information of internal stress/strain for a specified loading history which, for example, could have been obtained by the analysis of the global deformation. The proposed overall plasticity model can be a starting point for this kind of analysis. On the other hand, it is very desirable to relate the internal stress to one of the global deformation measures. For example, we found that the fiber stress is more related to the composite *elastic* strain than other measures, as shown in Figure 10 for three loading conditions, i.e., longitudinal, and transverse with $\eta = 0$ and $\eta = 0.6$. In these figures, the strains are in the fiber's direction. We wish to explore this kind of relation to facilitate the composite analysis in the future.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study employed the generalized Eshelby equivalent inclusion method to investigate the internal stress and plasticity of unidirectionally reinforced composites during longitudinal and transverse loading. Using the SiC/2014 Al system as an example, the general effects of fiber's aspect ratio were examined. Based on the same framework, an orthotropic yield function is proposed whose anisotropy parameters are determined by the calculated results from the generalized Eshelby method. Definite difference is observed between the proposed yield function and Hill's orthotropic yield function.

This study is far from completeness, instead, it opened up many more issues waiting to be explored through either theoretical or experimental efforts. We list some of them as follows. (1) The constrained flow behavior of matrix metal remains to be better understood and modelled. (2) It is a reasonable try to correlate the possibility of matrix debonding to the difference between the average fiber strain and the average matrix strain. (3) A deformation analysis of MMCs is possible by applying the proposed yield function and associated formulation. In addition, we should emphasize on how to recover the microscopic information (e.g., internal stress) from the results of global analysis. (4) The similar account should also be established for the thermal effects. One of the interesting problems is the superplasticity by thermal cycling.

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6. REFERENCES

1. German, R. M. and Bose, A., Materials Science and Engineering, Vol. A107, pp. 107-116, 1989.
2. Yang, J. M., Kao, W. H., and Liu, C. T., Materials Science and Engineering, Vol. A107, pp.81-91, 1989.
3. McKimpson, M. G. and Scott, T. E., Materials Science and Engineering, Vol. A107, pp.93-106, 1989.
4. Fishman, S. G. and Dhingra, A. K. (eds), Cast Reinforced Metal Composites, Proceedings of the Int. Symp. Advances in Case Reinforced Metal Composites, ASM International, 1988.
5. Arsenault, R. J., Materials Science and Engineering, Vol.64, pp.171-181, 1984.
6. Liu, Y. L., Hansen, N., and Jensen, D. J., Metall. Trans. Vol.20A, pp.1743-1753, 1989.
7. Almas, M. and Humphreys, F. J., in Strength of Metals and Alloys, P.O. Kettunen, T.K. Lepisto and M.E. Lehtonen (eds), ICSMA 8, Vol.3, pp. 1395-1400, 1988.
8. Nieh, T. G. and Kaplak, R. F., J. Materials Science Letters, Vol. 2, pp. 119-122, 1983.
9. Sugauma, K., Fujita, T., Niihara, K., Okamoto, T., Koizumi, M., and Suzuki, N., Materials Science and Technology, Vol. 5, pp. 249-254, 1989.
10. McDanel, D. L., Metall. Trans. A, Vol. 16A, pp. 1105-1115, 1985.
11. Needleman, A., J. Applied Mechanics, Paper No. 87-WA/APM-9.
12. Tszeng, T. C., Ohriner, E. K., and Sikka, V. K., submitted to Acta metall. mater., 1990.
13. Zweben, C., J. Mech. Phys. Solids, Vol. 22, pp. 193-215, 1974.
14. Kelly, A. and Tyson, W. R., in High-Strength Materials, edied by Zackay, V. F., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1964.
15. Wright, M. A. and Wills, J. L., J. Mech. Phys. Solids, Vol. 22, pp. 161-175, 1974.
16. Nairn, J. A., J. Composite Materials, Vol. 22, pp. 561-588, 1988.
17. Eshelby, J. D., Proc. R. Soc., Vol. A241, pp. 376, 1957.
18. Brown, L. M. and Clarke, D. R., Acta metall., Vol. 25, pp. 563-570, 1977.
19. Pedersen, O. B. and Brown, L. M., Acta metall., Vol. 25, pp. 1303-1305, 1977.
20. Withers, P. J., Stobbs, W. M., and Pedersen, O. B., Acta metall. Vol. 37, pp. 3061-3084, 1989.
21. Warner, T. J. and Stobbs, W. M., Acta metall. Vol. 37, pp. 2873-2881, 1989.
22. Pedersen, O. B., Acta metall. mater. Vol. 38, pp. 1201-1219, 1990.
23. Tszeng, T. C., submitted to ASME J. of Applied Mechanics, 1991.
24. Garmong, G., Metall. Trans., Vol. 5A, pp. 2183-2190, 1974.
25. Hill, R., The Mathematical Theory of Plasticity, Oxford University Press, London, 1950.
26. Sun, C. T. and Chen, J. L., J. Composite Materials, Vol. 23, pp.1009-1020, 1989.
27. Sun, C. T., Feng, W. H., and Koh, S. L., Int. J. Engng. Sci., Vol. 12, pp.919-935, 1974.
28. Kenaga, D., Doyle, J. E., and Sun, C. T., J. Composite Materials, Vol. 21, pp. 516-531, 1987.
29. Arsenault, R. J. and Taya, M., Acta metall. Vol.35, pp.651-659, 1987.

Figure 9. The yield surface on the plane of principal stress for composite undergoing plane stress deformation; 1 : Hill's model, $\epsilon P = 0.218\%$; 2 : the present model, $\epsilon P = 0.218\%$; 3: Hill's model, $\epsilon P = 0.779\%$; 4: the present model, $\epsilon P = 0.779\%$; Lines: plane strain, $---$: $\epsilon P = 0.218\%$, $---$: $\epsilon P = 0.779\%$;

Figure 10. Fiber stress as a function of the composite elastic strain in the fiber direction.